

Riga Technical University
Institute of Energy System and Environment

Questionnaire for

SOCIAL LIFE CYCLE ASSESSMENT FRAMEWORK

FOR THE TACO ALGAE PROJECT

1. INTRODUCTION: What is the Social Life Cycle Assessment?

The Social Life Cycle Assessment (S-LCA) is one of three methodologies that have been developed to assess the sustainability of the three Pillars of organizations, products, and services, focusing on the People Pillar. Thus, S-LCA is the framework to assess the social impacts of products and services across their life cycle. The S-LCA aims to assess social consequences (positive or negative) on different stakeholder categories:

Workers, the local community, society, consumers, value chain actors, and children are the main stakeholder categories reported in the UNEP “Guidelines for Social Life Cycle Assessment.” **However, based on system characteristics, it is also possible to expand this list to include more specific stakeholder categories.**

The social effects of the stakeholders can be measured on impact categories:

These impact categories summarized the list of social indicators based on the stakeholders:

- | - Worker | - Local community |
|---|---------------------------------------|
| 1. Freedom of association and collective bargaining | 1. Access to material resources |
| 2. Child labor | 2. Access to immaterial resources |
| 3. Fair salary | 3. Delocalization and migration |
| 4. Working hours | 4. Cultural heritage |
| 5. Forced labor | 5. Safe and healthy living conditions |
| 6. Equal opportunities/discrimination | 6. Respect for indigenous rights |
| 7. Health and safety | 7. Community engagement |
| 8. Social benefits/social security | 8. Local employment |
| 9. Employment relationship | 9. Secure living conditions |
| 10. Sexual harassment | |
| 11. Smallholders, including farmers | |

- **Society**

1. Public commitment to sustainability issues
2. Contribution to economic development
3. Prevention and mitigation of armed conflict
4. Technology development
5. Corruption
6. Ethical treatment of animals
7. Poverty alleviation

- **Value chain actors (not including consumers)**

1. Fair competition
2. Promoting social responsibility
3. Supplier relationship
4. Respect for intellectual property rights
5. Wealth distribution

- **Consumer**

1. Health and safety
2. Feedback mechanism
3. Consumer privacy
4. Transparency
5. End-of-life responsibility

2. INSTRUCTION FOR THE QUESTIONNAIRE COMPILATION

We would like to ask for your cooperation in filling out the following questionnaire.

The goal is to acquire opinions and information about potential social impact in the case of a seaweed biorefinery. We would be asked:

- To select which are the most representative type of stakeholder based on your experience and opinion;
- Select the most representative impact categories for each of the stakeholders.

3. THE QUESTIONNAIRE

1- Please select, based on opinion and expertise, which are the most representative **stakeholders** (you can select more than 1) for a seaweed biorefinery system from the list below:

- Worker
- Local community
- Society
- Consumers
- Value chain actors
- Children
- Others

Please, if you select others, specify here what:

2- Please select, based on opinion and expertise, which are the most representative **social indicators** (you can select more than 1) for the **Worker** stakeholder:

- Freedom of association and collective bargaining
- Child labor
- Fair salary
- Working hours
- Forced labor
- Equal opportunities/discrimination
- Health and safety
- Social benefits/social security
- Employment relationship
- Sexual harassment
- Smallholders including farmers
- Others

Please, if you select others, specify here what:

3- Please select, based on opinion and expertise, which are the most representative **social indicators** (you can select more than 1) for the **Local community** stakeholder:

- Access to material resources
- Access to immaterial resources
- Delocalization and migration
- Cultural heritage
- Safe and healthy living conditions
- Respect of indigenous rights
- Community engagement
- Local employment
- Secure living conditions
- Others

Please, if you select others, specify here what:

4- Please select, based on opinion and expertise, which are the most representative **social indicators** (you can select more than 1) for the **Society** stakeholder:

- Public commitment to sustainability issues
- Contribution to economic development
- Prevention and mitigation of armed conflict
- Technology development
- Corruption
- Ethical treatment of animals
- Poverty alleviation
- Others

Please, if you select others, specify here what:

5- Please select, based on opinion and expertise, which are the most representative **social indicators** (you can select more than 1) for the **Consumer** stakeholder:

- Health and safety
- Feedback mechanism
- Consumer privacy
- Transparency
- End-of-life responsibility
- Others

Please, if you select others, specify here what:

6- Please select, based on opinion and expertise, which are the most representative **social indicators** (you can select more than 1) for the **Value chain actors** stakeholder:

- Fair competition
- Promoting social responsibility
- Supplier relationship
- Respect of intellectual property rights
- Wealth distribution

Please, if you select others, specify here what:

7- Please, if you have selected **another stakeholder in question 1**, add here what kind of social indicators could be related to it:
